

PLURIVERSAL
DESIGNATION

THE FUTURE OF
PLURIVERSAL
DESIGNATION

© *Published Jan 2023*

0

1

THE FUTURE OF PLURIVERSAL DESIGN EDUCATION

CURRICULAR RECOMMENDATION AUTHORS

TEAM LEADS

Lesley-Ann Noel*

[North Carolina State University, USA]

Ronni Rosenberg*

[Retired, Sheridan College, Canada]

STEERING COMMITTEE LIAISONS

Gjoko Muratovski

[Deakin University, Australia]

Srini Srinivasan

[World Design Organization, Shanghai]

COMMITTEE MEMBERS

Shalini Agrawal

[California College of the Arts, USA]

Vikram Augustine

[Design Edge Consultancy, India]

Nii Botchway

[Nelson Mandela University, South Africa]

Alfredo Gutiérrez Borrero

[Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano, Colombia USA]

Edson Cabalfin

[Tulane University, USA]

Simon Charwey

[African Design Matters, Ghana]

Erico Fileno

[EY Design Studio LAS, Brazil]

Maria Cristina Ibarra

[Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil]

Ishan Khosla

[Ishan Khosla Design, India]

Arvind Lodaya

[Vidyashilp University, India]

Steve Ouditt

[University of the West Indies, Trinidad]

Ralitsa Diana Debrah

[Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana]

Sadie Red Wing

[Ontario College of Art and Design, Canada]

Natalie Robertson

[Auckland University of Technology, New Zealand]

Jorge Rodriguez

[Mexico]

Adolfo Ruiz

[MacEwan University, Canada]

Victor Udoewa

[NASA, USA]

Fred Van Amstel

[Federal University of Technology, Parana]

Neeta Verma

[University of Notre Dame, USA]

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Preamble..... 00

THEME 1.....00

Pluriversal Ways of Knowing and Making..... 00

List of Topics Within The Theme:.....00

Culturally Grounded Design Practice..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics..... 00

Resilience and Change..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics..... 00

Global Epistemologies – More Than Modern World Views..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics..... 00

New Roles for the Designer in the Pluriverse..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics..... 00

Critical Making..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics.....00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics.....00

Comparative Cross-Cultural Analyses.....00

Motivation.....00

Sub-Topics.....00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics.....00

THEME 2	00
Respectful Relationality	00
List of Topics Within The Theme:.....	00
<i>Relationality across cultures and worldviews and</i>	
<i>Relational Design Practice Community Engaged</i>	
<i>Design Practice: context-specific co-design</i>	
<i>and participatory design practices</i>	00
<i>Relational Design Practice</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Community-Engaged Design Practice</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Learning From “other” Worlds</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Learning With and From Each Other</i>	00

<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Learning with and from industry</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Design for Social Innovation and</i>	
<i>Community Impact</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Ethics, Respect and Radical Empathy</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics</i>	00
<i>Other than Human: Life-Centred Design</i>	00
<i>Motivation</i>	00
<i>Sub-Topics</i>	00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics.....00*

THEME 3.....00

**Pluriversal Design Strategies, Methods
and Content..... 00**

List of Topics Within The Theme:.....00

*Design Critique/Social Critique and
Context.....00*

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Theories of Sustainability.....00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Marginalised Design Histories..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Post-Industrial and Post-Capitalist Designs.... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Seeing and Visualizing Differences..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Criticising Cultural Stereotypes in Design.... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

*Values-Based Design Methodology
[Design and Values]..... 00*

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Design Ethnography and Anthropology.... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

THEME 4.....00

Pluriversal Design Research..... 00

List of Topics Within The Theme:.....00

Pluriversal Research Epistemologies.....00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

*Radical Imagining, Speculation and
Futuring.....00*

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Co-Design and Participatory Design..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

*Student-Centred Learning Outcomes
and Rubrics..... 00*

Understanding Oral Histories..... 00

Motivation..... 00

Sub-Topics..... 00

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes.... 00

Rubrics..... 00

Reframing Research.....00

THEME 5.....	00
Pluriversal Communication.....	00
List of Topics Within The Theme:.....	00
<i>Design and Storytelling.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-Topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-Topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Alternative Methods of Communication.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-Topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>and Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Other Courses for Consideration.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Cultural appropriation, hybridization,</i>	
<i>and appreciation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Archiving stories [Historiography].....</i>	<i>00</i>

THEME 6.....	00
Pluriversal Spaces of Learning.....	00
<i>Learning in Community.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-Topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Land-Based Learning.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Contextual Feedback - New Forms of</i>	
<i>Critique.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Motivation.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Sub-topics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Student-Centred Learning Outcomes....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Rubrics.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Generative themes and Big Ideas for</i>	
<i>Design Education.....</i>	<i>00</i>
<i>Ten Big Ideas for Pluriversal Design</i>	
<i>Education.....</i>	<i>00</i>

BACKGROUND

THE FDE INITIATIVES AND ITS GOALS

The Future of Design Education initiative was conceived and founded in late 2019 by a partnership between the Design Lab of the University of California, San Diego, and IBM's Global Design Group. The World Design Organization joined as a co-sponsor. The initiative was made of a small executive team, a Steering Committee composed of leading designers from academia and industry, and more than 600 volunteers ranging from undergraduate students to distinguished deans, department chairs, and industry executives representing every region of the world. These volunteers were part of working groups and provided overall assessment and advice in the content development process.

Workgroups

The Future of Design Education [FDE] initiative convened Working Groups for the development of themes that represent broad consensus and feedback from educational samples.

Each Working Group produced: a theme definition; a preamble that identified content scope and reflected concern for beliefs, principles, and characteristics of graduates; and a bulleted list of 5-10 topics that itemized the ideas. For each topic, the group determined whether it is core, specialized, or optional and provides a statement of desired Student Learning Outcomes with a rubric.

The Pluriversal Design Education working group assembled a diverse team of educators from around the world, aiming to understand how decoloniality, pluriversality, multi-centricity, indigeneity and reflexivity are currently being incorporated in hyper local design curricula. This lens shape guidelines for the future of design curriculum.

The Pluriversal Design Education working group met from April – September of 2021. This publication contains the results of their discussions. This document

shares the detailed content that led to the ten Big Ideas that are shared through the FDE initiative. The document opens with an essay that supports the readers' understanding of the core concepts that ground the big ideas. This essay was part of a draft that the working group aimed to publish in a journal. This is followed by a detailed description of curriculum content, finally the list of the ten Big Ideas is presented. This is a working document, and we look forward to seeing how the pluriversal design community builds on it.

December 2022

INTRODUCTION

1 Different communities in different parts of the world face unique challenges and opportunities. One global model of design education cannot be applicable to all. The work of the Pluriversal Design Education group recognized the wide variety of contexts in which design is taught and learned. This group focused on the experience of design practice from outside of the Global North, and outside the 'dominant' design culture, which is typically perceived as Euro American-centric and 'modern'. The group identified goals and values for a different type of design practice not based on a patriarchal-capitalist worldview.

Instead, the work of this group sought to develop a relational view of design, that prepared designers to live in harmony with the Earth.

This group acknowledged the significance of culturally relevant, local, and indigenous knowledges, including those that existed before the advent of colonialism and globalization, as well as the impact

that these knowledges could have on local and global design practice. The work of this group aims to converge epistemologies and methods of design practice from outside of the Global North. Rather than creating one set of design principles intended for universal uptake, our goal was to create a guiding framework through dialogue that enables all communities and cultures to act within the design discipline, from within their own epistemologies, supporting a way forward to a pluriversal and decolonial design education. The work acknowledged various acquisitions of knowledge by designers who practice within their communities and seek to bring this knowledge into their educational institutions. Finally, the work of this group considered the different places of learning within cultures that may be outside of the educational institution and considered non-traditional from a Western perspective.

Grounding Concepts

The work of this committee was grounded in pluriversal and decolonial principles, such as multi-centricity, indigeneity, and reflexivity, which Dei [2014] proposed as decolonial principles for curricula. Pluriversality provides a counternarrative to contemporary Northern assumptions of the universal. The concept of pluriversality is grounded in the idea that there is no 'universal' and the world is constituted through a multitude of knowledges and ways of being. Arturo Escobar defined the Pluriverse as being related to the Zapatista war motto of a "world in which many worlds can fit". In a stricter definition, the pluriverse can be defined as a universe that can be home to many conflicting universes. The pluriverse no longer stands as the opposite of universe, but as an unsettling synthesis of multiple universes. Then, the pluriverse does not deny the possibility of universalizing other concepts that are not worlds, such as nation, culture, land, life, etc [Gutierrez, 2022]. According to Vieira Pinto [2020], universality is just one path that connects consciousness to the totality of human experience. Without universals, though, human beings

cannot develop existential projects that are complex enough to afford differences.

Wallerstein [Reiter p.4] advocated for a move away from universal laws, and with this in mind, this group proposes pluriversal approaches that will not substitute one universal with a new universal but rather provide a framework where many different forms of design practice can co-exist. A pluriversal approach challenges the concept of universality, or one way of being, which is how design has been traditionally taught. Design has followed a particular trajectory and discourse due to its being defined and dominated by the West. One consequence of this is that its manifestation and body of work/achievements in other cultures remained invisibilized and delegitimized or exoticized. A pluriversal approach would open design up to an awareness that design is practiced by all humans and across all cultures in a variety of ways.

Pluriversal Design Education

Pluriversal design education is design education that acknowledges many ways of being and knowing outside of modern Western epistemologies. We need pluriversal design education that is locally informed, yet globally relevant. This kind of design education can help create a new generation of designers capable of advancing the interests of their own communities. For many diverse and globally underrepresented nations, pluriversal design can help strengthen three pillars of their everyday life: economic, cultural, and social. The expansion of the notion of designers are not merely decorators, artisans, and stylists, but also strategists, facilitators, and technologists, could ensure that designers play a leading role in all elements of the future of these communities.

Economy: There is not an adequate understanding in many small communities and postcolonial nations around the world of the power of design and its ability to improve local economies. Design could be a tool to reimagine and develop local economies in a more sustainable way. ***Without strong local economies,***

everything else will remain fragile. Design could be part of the mechanism to move production away from the export of raw resources, selling handcrafted folk art, or providing cheap labour to foreign companies.

Culture: In the face of Western hegemony, many communities and nations are not accepted as equal global actors and their cultures and knowledge are at times presented as inferior. This can have a significant negative effect on local self-worth and confidence, and as a result, their youth often feel embarrassed of their origin. Globalization has caused distinct cultural and national identities to become eroded and stagnated. Designers can play a role in reinvigorating local cultural identities by creating new contemporary visual expressions and languages. Cultures are living entities that must evolve in order to survive, and designers can inject new life into these distinct cultural expressions. ***Nations with strong cultural identities give their people the confidence that they are in control of their own destinies.***

Society: Some postcolonial societies inherited governance systems that were never designed for local people to flourish. They may have been created around colonial dominance and economic systems. Designers could play a role in reimagining transformative new systems for future generations that focus on thriving, living and wellbeing. By embracing service design, systems thinking and social innovation, designers today can help design new governance systems, new economies, and new social services that are informed by the unwritten and unspoken rules that define these communities. ***Self-reliant and independent societies are more resilient than interdependent ones.***

A pluriversal approach to design education could break up the singular 'grand narrative' of design into a multiplicity of local, rooted narratives - however, with a critical, rigorous, and caringly-negotiated consensus on overarching values and purpose - envisaging a plurality of narratives that may even contradict and conflict with each other at the micro-scale, but come together and align at the macro. This approach could

enable local histories and cultures of design to get 'discovered' and 'published' and incorporated into 'the mainstream' - also impacting it directly in terms of diversifying it and shifting its 'centre of gravity' away from the West - thus anticipating a fractal structure for the field. While this is one approach, members of the group also recognized that going hyper-local and rejecting universals does not favor the decolonization struggle. Instead, it tends to keep discrepancies as they are, incommensurable and therefore very consolable."

A pluriversal approach could also challenge the transactionality that has been criticized in design as the world moves away from Eurocentrism to recognizing more complexity and respecting more diverse perspectives. While traditionally, design is/has been transactional i.e., focusing on methods and practices that lead to design efficiency, collecting information in a way that focuses on benefits for the designer or their client, and rapid returns for the time spent in the design process. While transactions are needed in the design process, this group sought to focus on

relationality instead of transactionality. For this working group, a pluriversal approach would be relational rather than transactional. Relationality would centre trust building, longer-term commitments, focus on relationships over transactions, and a dedication to understanding and thriving.

Pluriversality is not about 'everything goes'. It became evident that despite an interest in letting all languages of design from all worlds be spoken and heard, there are some worlds that are incompatible with pluriversality, such as the design languages of a fascist dictator or far-right extremist groups. There is a line between a world that can fit many worlds and a world that cannot do it.

A discipline that rises through exclusion, oppression, and dominance can neither sustain itself nor grow deeper roots beyond its narrow approach. It is this very exclusion that brings us to this intersection. The concept of pluriversality resists, problematizes, and counters that approach while simultaneously leveraging the discipline through the intrinsic pluri-

versality [not universality] of design that does not default to a constructed core. Pluriversality is not diversity, equity, and inclusion. It is not only about culture. The paradigm shift here is towards a pluriversal consciousness, new ways of thinking about design [and design education] that arise out of relationality to create worldviews that have the propensity to embrace several worlds as opposed to one that destroys others. Whereas inclusion suggests convergence around a dominant perspective and worldview, pluriversality moves the discussion to divergence.

The work of this group of scholars with an interest in pluriversality is not merely about decoloniality. It is not a rant against the status quo. This work undertaken by this group is a hopeful, optimistic, and co-created utopic vision for the future of design education. A pluriversal approach to design education and practice should not be taken as the opposite of universality but rather as a plurality of localities reclaiming their right to universalize and reject oppressive universals. Pluriversal design is based on two premises: *a) pluriversal means life-affirming, and*

b] pluriversal favors worlds that do not destroy other worlds.

This pluriversal approach to design does not attempt to be a series of steps or methods that can be generalizable to all kinds of design practice.

The working group discussed different plural ways of doing design. Many of the discussions began with the idea that a pluriversal approach facilitates communication across languages and cultures, ensuring that many have a voice, and that relationships and experience are valued. This approach made it easy to see and elevate 'the local' in design practices.

Pluriversality can also be conceived as an educational quality that attempts to expand definitions of design, acknowledge alternate design methodologies, and seeks to include diverse design. Its main feature is broadening the contexts within which design is defined in an attempt to conceive an alternate future for this branch of knowledge. It is an endeavour that lays a path forward for design education that is inclusive, diverse, and equitable in the way it reframes

this discipline that lies at the core of human cultural experiences and identities. Through the multiple lenses of ontologies, culture, epistemology, globality, and locality, students will explore the richness of design as practiced in different contexts, ecologies, and societies.

The central argument of the ideas proposed here is that whereas past iterations of design focused on artifacts, moving forward, design will be relational, not object or artifact based.

- A] The future of design is relational, not artifact based.*
- B] Design is practiced everywhere in a variety of ways across the globe, and these diverse practices can inform all design practices.*
- C] Diverse perspectives are needed for a more complex understanding of issues*
- D] New ontologies will lead to new design approaches to design practice such as more philosophical and ecological approaches.*

The design approaches emphasize consciousness and critical awareness that lead to design conducive to the planet and environment.

ONTOLOGICAL
DESIGN

ONTOLOGICAL DESIGN

Some of the issues explored through the Pluriversal working group had to do with how different ways of knowing can continue to flourish within our shared household: Mother Earth, Gaia, or Papatūānuku. Furthermore, issues of pluriversality lead us to consider if it is at all possible to restore the root meaning of economy, as an enduring system that contributes to the flourishing rather than destruction of this household.

1

The working group directly and indirectly explored these ideas. Presentations that led the group discussions were often rooted in places, cultural memory, and local knowledge from different parts of the world. The approach was “to start with the ground on which we stand” [McIntosh,pg.34(1)].

Such an approach may seem traditional, rooted in the past, and local. The group, however, considers traditional and local knowledge as a way forward, in order to conceive alternative futures. Traditional ways

of knowing are possible tools upon which to build a future design education. Following, among other things, perspectives derived from the Global South, and the Indigenous world, these ideas are valuable “tools for criticism, futuring” and “sustainment” [Escobar,pg.128 (2)].

Rather than thinking of the past as romantic or nostalgic, traditional and/or local knowledge, oral history, and land-based know-how offer vital perspectives from which to rethink design, while suggesting new perspectives regarding many of the complex problems of the present time. As Winograd and Flores [in Escobar, pg. 116 (3)] write: “Ontologically oriented design is... necessarily both reflective and political, looking back to the traditions that have formed us but also forward to as-yet uncreated transformations of our lives together.”

Ideas about ontological design discussed thus far align with a holistic [as opposed to mechanistic] way

7

of thinking. An overarching concept often referenced through this working group is that all things are interconnected and interdependent—“as individuals and societies, we are all embedded in [and dependent on] cyclical processes of nature” [Capra and Luisi, pg. 12 (4)].

1 The notion of cyclical or circular processes is a core aspect of ontological design. In the most basic terms, ontological design is based on a circular relation between human [design] activity, and [designed] world—with each one shaping the other [as in a feedback loop]. The idea can be described in many different ways. For example, the creation of tools and technology leads to actions that modify ways of being in the world, which in turn modify the very way in which people further create tools and technology. As Anne-Marie Willis [(5) (6) pg. 82] writes, “we design our world, while our world acts back on us and designs us.”

This circular concept can prompt thoughtful engagement with the ramifications and responsibilities

involved in design practice and education. Ontological design forces people to seriously consider the extent to which tangible and intangible forms of cultural production are entangled in ways of sensing, thinking, and being in the world. Such considerations require an understanding of reality that moves beyond Cartesian dualistic thinking.

8 One of the most distinctive characteristics of Cartesian philosophy is the mind/matter duality. Through this duality, the world appears to be divided in two realms—on the one hand, the realm of human/mind [source of agency]; on the other hand, the realm of non-human, non-living things [with no agency] that humans willfully manipulate and use. This duality was a foundational concept behind the Scientific Revolution of the seventeenth century [and the creation of the modern world as we know it] [Capra and Luisi, pg. 23 (7)].

From the perspective of ontological design, however, the mind/matter duality proves inadequate as an interpretive lens through which to understand reality.

Instead, ontological design requires a more complex understanding regarding the realms of mind and matter—rather than a clear division, the boundary between the two can be thought of as fuzzy or even dissolving. Furthermore, the Cartesian presumption of matter as lifeless is also challenged from this perspective.

To put it simply, the things we make possess agency—from computers and cars to politics and policies. This idea not only challenges Western dualistic thinking, but it also forces us to consider the role played by non-human, ‘non-living’ actors [that we design] and in turn design us back, and shape our ways of being.

To conclude this section, it is worth considering that ontological design elicits a range of perspectives that align with ecological interpretations of the world. Moving beyond the Cartesian view of the world as a lifeless mechanical system, ontological design has implications for how design educators think about the many entities, living and non-living, that populate the world [including the things we design]. This circular

concept may also help promote a new perspective on the relation between humans and the earth. Such a perspective is urgently needed in the Global North. As Hispanic-Apache philosopher Viola Cordova [pg. 210 (8)] notes: the notion that “humans are somehow superior to the Earth itself, that humans are separate and apart from all else” hinders new thinking about environmental ethics and our place in the world. Ontological design is, in essence, a relational worldview that can help elicit careful consideration of our place within this shared household we call Earth.

In unpacking ontological design, this section has explored reductionist understandings of the lifeworld, issues of ecology, technology and the circular relation between humans and world. This concluding part of the section describes the scope and implications of an ontological design perspective. To begin illustrating the implications of adopting this perspective, it is worth noting that ontological design is not merely a separate, new, and different kind of design – instead, all design is ontological. Everything we design has potency and power to design us back and affect our

ways of being and knowing. Everything we have ever designed has always had this agency.

The question is this: Are we aware that what we design affects our ways of being and knowing? And with that awareness, can we intentionally design anything for healthier ways of being and knowing? This awareness and intentionality with the holistic consequences of our designs is the ontological approach.

2 The ontological approach is neutral in the eyes of certain scholars. This group embodies an ontological approach with a bias towards the pluralistic multiverse – the pluriverse. In other words, a pluriversal bias of ontological design, proposed here, mean sseeking to see trans-local communities engaging in autonomous design towards their own desire-based vision of their future, not conforming to any totalizing, cannibalising mono-humanism. In other words, can there be a world of many worlds or many centres [pluriverse] instead of a world of one world or centre [universe]?

0 Ontological design is not just about visual design and decolonizing the monopolizing Americo-Eurocentrism in aesthetics that has marginalized and side-lined different ways of being beautiful and seeing and knowing knowing beauty. No, this is about all types of design – UX/UI design, organizational design, service design, learning design, the design of economic systems, communication design, the design of political systems, the design of innovation methodologies, and even the design of design, itself. When viewed through an ontological lens, one can see how our entire modern world has been designed from a modernist, cartesian, dualist, scientific rationalist, extractivist, transactionalist, objectivist, positivist way of being and knowing – our political systems, histories, economic systems, organizations, reporting structures, financial instruments, governments, schools, multilateral organizations, and more.

GENERATIVE THEMES AND BIG IDEAS FOR DESIGN EDUCATION

Big ideas are universal ideas, and this working group sought not to create new universals to replace old ones. In the discussions, the group recognized that the big Ideas should look different when realized in different places and contexts. The working group built its ideas by discussing six generative themes, which are listed below alongside the guiding principles of each discussion.

2

1

SIX BIG THEMES

2

2

THEME 1

PLURIVERSAL WAYS OF KNOWING AND MAKING

Design is a core component of almost every culture in the world, as it is a fundamental, evolutionary human impulse [one might argue, in other life forms, too]. Pluriversality becomes a counter-narrative to contemporary Northern assumptions of the universal, by including and legitimizing the diversity of design cultures around the world, and exposing students to many ways of knowing and being. Through the multiple lenses of culture, epistemology, globality and locality, students will explore the richness of design as practiced in different contexts, ecologies, and societies. This section will emphasize and celebrate this diversity and critically probe notions of “universal.”

AKPA

A Symbol of Knowledge and Wisdom

THEME 2WO

H.N.M.E.I S.E.E

A Symbol of Respect

RESPECTFUL RELATIONALITY

Designers are often tasked with designing solutions for people with cultural identities different from their own. Ideally, this should be a process of co-creation, and as such this becomes a process of relationship building. Then again, the way relationships are built and maintained in the Global South and the Global North varies markedly. Creating meaningful and mutually respectful cross-cultural relationships can be more challenging than most people think.

When people in different cultures who hold different beliefs come into a relationship, deeply rooted feelings of loyalty to one's own culture may impede the relationship. The culture of those in power *[or perceived power]*

may dominate the discourse. In order to avoid such unhealthy power imbalances when working in culturally diverse communities, designers must learn to accept and understand each other's cultural differences.

This is by no means an easy task, as culture is for the most part invisible. We hardly notice the distinctiveness of our own cultures until we're forced to see our behaviours and beliefs from another perspective. Therefore, the focus of this theme will be on intercultural and cross-cultural design relationality and co-creation, as it is practiced between students, faculty and with community--but in addition, consideration of non-human relationality needs to be considered, as designers interact with their environments.

THEME THREE

ATSIKI OYI

A symbol of Appropriateness.

The appropriate tool should be used for the right task.

PLURIVERSAL DESIGN STRATEGIES, METHODS AND CONTENT

In this theme, we seek to deconstruct and dismantle the universalized cultural agenda of design, re-locate it into the students' own home/native cultural contexts [and/or any other as applicable], and help them re-envision and re-assemble it therein, so that it adds up to what already exists instead of replacing or imposing a new order. We understand that in many cases, the local culture may not be homogenous or unproblematic either, and our aim is to sensitize and equip the student to empathetically, sensitively, critically, and creatively unpack the various layers and problematics involved, and articulate her/his/their own distinctive contribution in an informed and reflexive way.

THEME 4 OUR

ASRAFOI

Strategic thinking helps to bridge between where you are and where you want to be.

PLURIVERSAL DESIGN RESEARCH

Design research situated in pluriversality will evolve in different ways from a design research cantered in 'modernity'. Futuring will lead to a space for generating conversations around new possibilities for human and other-than-human flourishing.

The subject of pluriversal research, as an always caring disposition in the making, guides students to recognize the immensity, heterogeneity, and often overlooked wisdoms and practices, that need to be translated, creating greater respect for "other" wisdoms. A seminal assumption here is that those outside the academic-disciplinary field live and bring into existence their own "worlds." Therefore, pluriversal design research

provides practitioners with elements to respectfully approach otherness, and recognize differences and **divergences** [language, location, culture, spirituality, class, ethnicity, gender, species, etc]. **This process should not project the political performance known as the hegemonologue.** This is a voice that excludes, denies, or erases all others and is often infused with euro modern and anthropocentric biases.

THEME 5IVE

2

AKROMADIO

A symbol of Honesty and Frankness.

9

PLURIVERSAL COMMUNICATION

Communication is foundational to a design education. We will explore aspects of speech and representation across text, image, and audio. As learners situate their own communities in relation to other global communities, they will cast a critical eye on the representation of culture across the globe. Of critical importance as well will be a focus on different cultural modalities of narrativity and storytelling. In this topic we seek to explore global narratives and methods of storytelling, cultural origin stories and methods. This theme is driven by local origins stories, microhistories, mythologies, and practices to support design students as they find their voice in their practice. Different driving themes may be land-based, sea-based, nature-based, time-

based. There are many different ways of seeing the world, some are rooted in ecology, time, cosmology, cultural memory, ways of knowing, and intergenerational transmission of knowledge. Design is, therefore, about communicating ideas, and this requires the skill of storytelling, making creative use of language, images, and shared histories. This is a vital skill for design students, and can be situated in local cultures. This is also an opportunity for cross-cultural communication as students can compare communication and storytelling myths and methods across different groups, identifying similarities and differences in these practices.

THEME SIX

ATOABI

Nobody should be underrated or belittled.
Everyone has a purpose.

SPACES OF LEARNING

The various environments, physical and virtual contexts of how we teach and learn have embedded issues of inclusion and exclusion. Traditionally, the physical studio has been the space for learning and making. In a more diverse design context, the land and the community may also be significant places of learning.

Empowering education is situated [Shor, 1992] and therefore sites external to the studios of the educational institutions will also be important venues to embed the curriculum in local culture and contexts, promoting cultural awareness and connections.

This working group agrees that there is an urgent need for a collective shift in consciousness. The members also recognize, however, the challenge of prompting such large-scale change. Acknowledging the enormous complexity involved in transforming dominant interpretations of reality, this group has often referenced traditional ecological knowledge from the indigenous world as both a way of knowing and a form of environmental stewardship—offering a human ecological experience that is situated outside the Global North. A 2018 article from National Geographic speaks to this point:

3

Recent research demonstrates that while the world’s 370 million indigenous peoples make up less than five percent of the total human population, they manage or hold tenure over 25 percent of the world’s land surface and support about 80 percent of the global biodiversity” [16 Nov 2018, National Geographic].

This quote offers an important reminder of the limitations in universalist and monocultural approaches to design. The Pluriversal Working Group recognizes the need to fundamentally reframe dominant under-

standings of design. Part of this reframing will require learning from the “less than 5% of the human population”—Indigenous knowledge holders.

Dominant models of design education, rooted in the Global North support a Eurocentric form of consciousness that reinforces the status quo of capitalist modernity. This group advocates for greater awareness of the many varied ways of knowing—or different manifestations of consciousness – that make up the pluriversality of life on planet earth. As discussed earlier, multiple ways of knowing – biodiversity and cultural diversity – are both vital to the future of humanity. This group also believes that pluriversal consciousness equals what design actually is. As described earlier, design is practiced everywhere, in a variety of ways across the globe; therefore, pluriversal design embodies the diversity of human knowledge that has existed since time immemorial.

2

CONCLUDING REMARKS

We are not interested in training designers adapted to an existing [oppressive] reality. We train them to transform their realities and a pluriversal and ontological approach is needed in design education to achieve these aims. If ontological design is about transforming reality, then pluriversal or ontological design cannot be reduced to storytelling across cultures. Ontology is not about subjective experience; it is about objective reality. Everything that constitutes a given reality must be changed: structures, materials, policies, and everything else. Conveying this message through stories is a minor part of it. Framing the pluriverse as a mere dispute of narratives is losing the dispute for the affordance of the world that can fit many worlds.

The ontological nature of pluriversal design shifts design from artifacts to “ways of being.” This type of design is negotiated through active participation by all stakeholders. A pluriversal approach to design is not about working in other parts of the world as a

designer it is about embodying design in new ways of being, and this is the overarching concept of the principles that are put forth by this group.

We learned to see each other and develop intersubjective consciousness, being conscious and acknowledging the difference of another consciousness. This is mutual recognition in alterity relations, the encounter that finds the other in the self and the self in the other. Further to our initial mission of exploring different viewpoints from around the world, the Pluriversal group generated an important social space that brought together a range of perspectives. As with biodiversity, the cultural diversity of this group facilitated a fruitful exchange of knowledge – a cross-fertilization of ideas that generated key points discussed in this paper. The future of design education [and practice] will benefit from a similar intercultural way of thinking—explicitly stating diversity of culture and thought as its starting point.

A pluriversal approach to design is not generalizable to all kinds of design practice. A pluriversal approach to design education and practice should not be taken as the opposite of universality but rather as a plurality of localities reclaiming their right to universalize and reject oppressive universals. Even if we are diverse, there are underrepresented worlds that would never be able to be heard in this discussion. That is why we need to keep open minds for new challenges coming from new ones who join design education.

3 Design is a core component of almost every culture in the world, as it is a fundamental, evolutionary human impulse [one might argue, in other life forms, too]. Pluriversality becomes a counter-narrative to contemporary Northern assumptions of the universal by including and legitimising the diversity of design cultures around the world and exposing students to many ways of knowing and being. Through the multiple lenses of culture, epistemology, globality, and locality, students will explore the richness of design as practised in different contexts, ecologies, and societies. This section will emphasise and celebrate this diversity and critically probe notions of “universal.”

List of Topics Within The Theme:

1. *Culture and Culturally Grounded Design Practice.*
 2. *Resilience and Change [Change, Disrupt, Act].*
 3. *Dialogues across cultures.*
 4. *Philosophy: Introduction to Global epistemologies and world views, more than ‘modern’.*
 5. *Design otherwise: context-driven new roles for design in the pluriverse [designer as facilitator, activist, public, educator, entrepreneur etc.].*
 6. *Co-validation across cultures. Students learn to articulate differences and acceptance of other cultural systems.*
 7. *Critical Making.*
- 5

Culturally Grounded Design Practice

Motivation:

Designers' work is driven by specific cultural world-views, which will vary across the globe. In this course, learners will use an analytical framework to understand how culture shapes values, which in turn shapes design ideas. Learners will acquire tools to appreciate cultural differences and to interrogate tacit values that underlie forms of cultural production within different societies. This will support a culturally grounded design practice.

3

Sub-Topics:

- Theories of culture
- Applied understanding of culture
- Culture in Action - tacit values and cultural production
- Design as a subculture around the world

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Differentiate local design culture from others across the world
- Analyse power dynamics embedded in design cultures
- Synthesise moral and ethical positions to be reflected in design proposals

6

Resilience and Change

Motivation:

What can we learn from disruptive events – including “acts of God” – that threaten social well-being. What are adaptive, resilient social responses to crises? How can we study resilience in this context to inform strategies of proactive social change that promote well-being? What are the psycho-social dimensions learners need to investigate in order to develop a trauma-informed design practice? Do we need to redefine the scope, purpose, and impact of design to accommodate pluriversality and planetary challenges?

3

Sub-Topics:

- Cognitive behavioural therapy as a model for resilience
- Design practices informed by resilience and change [Trauma-informed design practice, jugaad, Cuban 1950s cars...]
- Responding to crises...
- Learning from crisis to drive change
- Envisioning new futures

- Strategies for resilience
- Caretaking, maintenance, and repair as strategies for resilience

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Differentiate local design subcultures from other subcultures across the globe
- Analyse power dynamics of existing design cultures
- Synthesise moral and ethical positions as part of design proposals

7

Global Epistemologies – More Than Modern World Views

Motivation:

The history of the design discipline is deeply steeped in Modernism ever since the Bauhaus codified the precepts of design education over one hundred years ago. What are the implications that flow from this perspective? How might a design education need to counter this perspective? What aspects of this legacy are worth preserving, and yet where may cultural damage have been done? This course will explore the modernist perspective and associated economic model in juxtaposition with post-modern counter narratives.

3

Sub-Topics:

- Understanding epistemology
- Analysis of pre-modern
- Analysis of modern
- Analysis of postmodern
- Analysing the influence of the Bauhaus
- Cultural impact of industrial modernity and colonialism

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse local design culture as part of political economy and hegemony
- Identify local design non-conforming sub-cultures that embody acts of resistance to the dominant culture
- Design proposals that serve to empower marginalised communities and sub-cultures

8

New Roles For The Designer In The Pluriverse

Motivation:

Since the Bauhaus, a Eurocentric view of design education has largely prevailed. As such, it has largely envisioned design education as a training ground for graduates to create artefacts prompted by clients in industry. How might we consider a 21st century design education that envisions a less Eurocentric view of design, where we might create deeper and broader notions of a design practice beyond relationships defined by industry commissions? How do we prepare designers who will be more socially engaged and who might partner with community members and institutions in order to facilitate and guide change? The role of a designer is expanding to include the design of systems, spaces, and services. How do we prepare the new designer to be effective both within and outside of the creative industries? How can designers help reclaim and revive local design subcultures that have been marginalised?

3

Sub-Topics:

- Mapping and integrating abilities across design disciplines “The Designs”
- The designed object in context: systems, services, spaces

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse local and immediate culture for constituent influences and origins
- Analyse ethical, spiritual, and aesthetic components of a design culture
- Research and track how cultures evolve over time and assimilate various influences
- Analyse “modernity” as a driver of culture

9

Critical Making

Motivation:

The work of this course will build on the ideas inherent in the term “Critical Making” coined by Matt Ratto in 2008, and constructionist educational theory. Through the process of making and interacting with materials, learners reflect on materiality, sustainability, and alternative modes of production. By focusing on process and experimentation, learners make more mindful design decisions regarding the use of materials, technological mediation, and responses to social issues.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Renewable and non-renewable materials
- Maintenance, repair, and sustainability
- Learning from co-production and collaboration
- Exploration of technological mediation of objects and systems

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse one’s positionality with regard to economic hegemony and sites of resistance
- Develop metrics and rubrics to assess the effectiveness of the designer’s role
- Stake personal responsibility for plotting personal learning journey in and out of the academic environment

0

Comparative Cross-Cultural Analyses

Motivation:

Learners will unpack the cultural values and valences inherent in visual representation across the globe. Through analysis and research, learners will develop deeper insights into human behaviours across cultures and test design ideas accordingly. Learners will also gain a deeper understanding of the values vested in cultural artefacts and differentiate between cultural appreciation and marketplace commodification.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Cultural dimensions theory
- Tools of ethnographic research

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Use various research methods, including design research, social sciences research, and anthropology research methods, to analyse values across cultures
- Test design ideas in a cultural context
- Research cultural appreciation with ethnographic tools
- Differentiate between cultural appreciation and marketplace commodification

1

Designers are often tasked with designing solutions for people with cultural identities different from their own. Ideally, this should be a process of co-creation, and as such, this becomes a process of relationship building. Then again, the way relationships are built and maintained in the Global South, and the Global North varies markedly. Creating meaningful and mutually respectful cross-cultural relationships can be more challenging than most people think.

4

When people in different cultures who hold different beliefs come into a relationship, deeply rooted feelings of loyalty to one's own culture may impede the relationship. The culture of those in power [or perceived power] may dominate the discourse. In order to avoid such unhealthy power imbalances when working in culturally diverse communities, designers must learn to accept and understand each other's cultural differences.

This is by no means an easy task, as culture is, for the most part, invisible. We hardly notice the distinctiveness of our own cultures until we're forced to see our behaviours and beliefs from another perspective. Therefore, the focus of this theme will be on intercultural and cross-cultural design relationality and co-creation, as it is practised between students, faculty, and with the community - but in addition, consideration of non-human relationality needs to be considered as designers interact with their environments.

2

List Of Topics Within The Theme:

Relationality across cultures and worldviews and Relational Design Practice Community Engaged Design Practice: context-specific co-design and participatory design practices

1. *Learning from “other” “worlds”: design ethics and practices of cross cultural and international collaborations - Cultural sensitivity, Anthropology, Ethnography [Intentional Listening and Seeing, ambiguity tolerance, understanding different design sensibilities]*
2. *Learning with and from each other: student collaborations*
3. *Learning with and from ‘industry’ on different scales [handicraft production, micro - macro entrepreneurs and makers]*
4. *Social Innovation partnerships: collaboration from activist groups to local and national government*

5. *Ethics, Respect and Radical Empathy: practices for respectful and empathetic design and mutuality*
6. *Other than human-centred design, posthumanism, culture and nature, life-centred design*

Relational Design Practice

Motivation:

The theme of collaborations and respectful relationships will explore the dynamic aspects of designing for, with, and by people in the contexts of their specific environments. Students learn how the processes of designing and purpose of design are constantly regenerated by the people and communities who are engaged with them, rather than when imposed by a unilateral designer. Students will theorise a relational design practice and process that accepts a dynamic and indeterminate mode of being and respects principles of sustainability, social justice, and flourishing.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Relationality within a community
- Relationality across cultures
- Feminist perspectives on power
- Human flourishing and the Anthropocene
- Emergence of the Global North and South

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Differentiate between dualist and non-dualist epistemologies
- Analyse design process from a unitary power perspective
- Analyse design process from a relational perspective
- Forecast potential environmental benefits from a relational design process

Community-Engaged Design Practice

Motivation:

The theme of Community Engaged Design Practice will explore how designers work with communities, both within their cultures and across different cultures. The relationship with communities is more of a partnership and is different from client-type relationships in industry. However, care must be taken for these partnerships to be stewarded by knowledgeable academic leaders, well practised in such facilitation.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Building Trust
- Facilitating Conversations
- Understanding Power dynamics [sharing power]
- Community History
- Sharing and Storytelling

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Demonstrate how unspoken power dynamics affect the community-based collaboration
- Facilitate group discussions, seeking the right kinds of input from group members

Learning From “Other” Worlds

Motivation:

The theme of Learning from other worlds will interrogate people’s cultural assumptions. Students will reflect on who is ‘othered’ and reflectively ‘other’ themselves by examining their own positionality in relation to marginalisation, and seeing how they are implicated in the ‘othering’ process. Students will explore their own historically included and historically excluded identities.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Understanding positionality
- A framework for learning with and from other groups and cultures
- Exploring different worldviews
- Understanding ‘value’ and what has been historically valued across different cultures

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Challenge cultural assumptions
- Analyse personal and collective positionality
- Create and utilise research frameworks to compare cultural values across the world
- Explore different worldviews

5

Learning With and From Each Other

Motivation:

The course aims to dispel the myth of the individual designer. Successful designers work with others, such as with user groups and in teams. The theme of “Learning with and from each other” will explore the dynamics of team collaboration and the importance of communication. Working in teams also ladders into leadership skills and interfacing with external groups. This course will develop the social and emotional intelligence abilities of the learners.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Team collaboration
- Leadership strategies
- Empathetic collaboration
- Communication

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Develop awareness of listening
- Enumerate tools of collaboration
- Refine communication skills
- Facilitate teamwork

Learning With and From Industry

Motivation:

Industry can be defined at different scales of production, from small-scale cottage production to large global industries. This theme will explore design practices and modes of research common in industry that students can partner with and learn from. Practices in industry will be explored on various scales of production, from handicrafts to larger-scale objects and systems.

6

Sub-Topics:

- Defining industry
- Research processes and scales of production
- Researching design practices

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Differentiate different scales of practice and modes of production [local vs. global, micro, vs. macro, entrepreneurial vs. large corporation]
- Reimagine what industry can be
- Propose alternative modes of practice and production
- Analyse the effectiveness of the industry at various scales.

4

Design for Social Innovation & Community Impact

Motivation:

Social innovation can take place at various scales of interaction, whether initiatives take place at micro, grassroots levels, or with larger, more fully funded group efforts.

Sub-Topics:

- Defining social innovation
- Establishing community relationships and partnerships
- Facilitating community conversations
- Identifying and Responding to community stressors through prototypes
- Co-Design with community stakeholders

7

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Scan the community to identify who are the actors already operating in the space
- Propose facilitation briefs for community interactions
- Identify precedents and gaps to know what the existing landscape around the issue is
- Employ co-design methods

Ethics, Respect and Radical Empathy

Motivation:

Students need to examine cultural assumptions of their design processes and objects and how they may be received by various global cultures. Students will analyse how such design processes and products have the capacity to exclude or harm certain individuals and communities. A grounding in radical empathy is foundational to such investigations.

4

This course will tie the concepts of ethics, respect, and radical empathy as integral to the process and outcome of design.

Sub-Topics:

- Relationality
- Ethics
- Respectful collaboration
- Radical empathy

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Describe the learning experiences of sister groups in different parts of the world
- Identify potential challenges experienced by various local communities
- Engage in respectful exploration with community partners
- Propose design solutions and analyse the impact on wellbeing

8

Other Than Human: Life-Centred Design

Motivation:

Design has traditionally focused on human-centred needs in order to drive outcomes. However, increasingly our scope of vision as designers considers the Anthropocene and the impact on all forms of life that designing processes can have. This course will encourage students to consider inputs and outputs from environmental sources other than humans, with an emphasis on interdependence and relationality.

4

Sub-Topics:

- Learning from biological processes
- Studying the impact reach of a product
- Impact of resource extraction across species and natural elements
- Product design in context: a case study

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse resource extraction as a result of a design outcome
- Differentiate between circular design processes and resource extraction

9

In this theme, we seek to deconstruct and dismantle the universalized cultural agenda of design, relocate it into the students' own home/native cultural contexts [and/or any other as applicable], and help them re-envision and re-assemble it therein, so that it adds up to what already exists instead of replacing or imposing a new order. We understand that in many cases, the local culture may not be homogenous or unproblematic either, and our aim is to sensitise and equip the student to empathetically, sensitively, critically, and creatively unpack the various layers and problematics involved and articulate her/his/their own distinctive contribution in an informed and reflexive way. We also recognize coloniality of design methods and the need for the decolonization of design activities.

5

List of Topics Within The Theme:

1. *Design critique / social critique in context*
2. *Theories of sustainability*
3. *Marginalised design histories*
4. *Post-Industrial and post-capitalist designs*
5. *Seeing and visualising differences*
6. *Critiquing cultural stereotypes in design*
7. *Values-based design methodology*
8. *Design ethnography and anthropology*

0

Design Critique / Social Critique and Context

Motivation:

The theme of Design Critique and Social Critique and Context encourages students to critique both the world around them and the work that they produce not just from a design perspective, but also from a social perspective. This course provides the language that is needed to critique designs in social, cultural, historical, and political contexts, taking into account the typical overlaps between these contexts. As a result of that, students will learn to situate their work in larger and longer contexts, enabling them to contribute to larger and longer processes of transformation in society. They will learn to problematize society in terms of design as well as to problematize design in terms of society.

Sub-Topics:

- Cultural hybridization: strength or erasure
- Vernacular and indigenous knowledges
- Design as self-actualization

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse the origin of cultural ideas
- Differentiate and compare cultures
- Analyse cultural influences on design systems and design objects
- Situate own work in a local and global context

Theories of Sustainability

Motivation:

The theme "Theories of Sustainability" will introduce students to processes, systems, and attributes that are required to keep design sustainable, specifically those found in indigenous craft sectors. Students acquire a theoretical framework to consider the effects of disruption, change, and building new worlds. They will also learn about diverse forms of sustainability for and from different contexts and worldviews. They will learn from historical, vernacular practices of maintenance, sustainability, and design, considering materiality, systems, and ways of thinking.

Sub-Topics:

- Sustainable systems
- Sustainable built world
- Sustainable natural world
- Sustainable change
- Histories and cultures of sustainability

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse the aspects to consider that impact sustainability [breakpoints / weak points]
- Identify and describe impact of sustainable practice on people and systems
- Differentiate theoretically between material, systemic and social implications of sustainability.
- Forecast potential actors and participants in sustainable practices

Marginalised Design Histories

Motivation:

Design, as it is currently defined, is a fairly recent discipline. However, it is an activity that humans have en-

gaged in for centuries in cultures across the globe. Current design histories tend to favour the Western model, which focuses on Eurocentricity and often ignores the many influences across regions.

This topic documents and criticises the Eurocentric focus in order to arrive at marginalised design histories and inform cultural identities. This will be accomplished using historiographic approaches based on other critical theories such as Indigenous Perspectives, Critical Race Theory, Decolonial Theory, Feminist Theory, and other theories that can recognize and value what happens at the margins of society. This topic will consider different geographies and different cultures and their role in design, moving design history away from its traditional focus on white, male, Europe, and North America towards a more global and critical view of design history.

Sub-Topics:

- Historiography: critical understanding of the tools and process of history formation
- Design history and impact on shaping culture
- Local and hidden design histories
- Dominant historical narratives and relative cultural values
- Relationship of historical narrative, material archives
- History of the relationships of material and materiality to culture

5

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Utilise the tools of recording history
- Deploy the tools of historiography
- Analyse the process of "writing history"
- Analyse the relationship between dominant historical narratives and culture
- Interpret local design histories in relation to each other
- Reveal hidden histories
- Analyse the process of how some "histories" come to be the dominant narrative

- Understanding when and how did specific schools of thought started displacing traditionally sustaining narratives and how it has influenced attitudes, philosophies and practice
- Documenting indigenous contributions to the discipline
- Who are the leaders whose thought or practice has influenced the way we think about the role and responsibility of design

Post-Industrial and Post-Capitalist Designs

3

Motivation:

This course challenges the industrial / commercial model of designing for profit, efficiency, convenience, and optimization. Instead, learners engage with the design development process to interrogate social issues and methods of response through design interventions. This assumes a more critical awareness of social issues and a desire for social repair.

Sub-Topics:

- Designing for non-profit
- Compare different movements in Critical Design [Global South focus on social justice, community, social change etc; Global North focus on technology, more than human etc]

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Investigate the impact of mass production as an economic model
- Analyse historical shifts in the production/consumption scale
- Analyse the role of consumerism in creating redundant needs.
- Examining the role of designers viz-à-viz sustainability
- Synthesise a design contribution for indigenous craft cottage industries
- Research the pre-industrial

5

Seeing and Visualizing Differences

Motivation:

Human perception is trained to seek patterns and ignore differences. Too often, new information emerges precisely from breaking this training and seeing overlooked differences. Once seen, differences can be visualised through external means that extend from individual perception to collective perception.

By exploring traditional as well as alternative ways of visual communication, designers can develop perceptual lenses to see differences and visual languages to visualise differences.

Sub-Topics:

- How designers use visualisation
- Cognitive functioning - how visualisation enhances / impedes understanding
- Cognitive biases and prejudices
- A survey of different methods of visualisation [Cartesian grids, Sign language, Semaphore, morse, alphabets... etc]
- Alternative typographies

4

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Identify attitudes towards imagery in localised cultures?
- Analyse attitudes towards the written word?
- Research the dominant modes of communication? Roles of the written word [print and display], sound mnemonic constructions, touch [role of haptics] and rhythm,
- Research the predominant systems of dissemination of information?
- Differentiate traditional methods of representation
- Identify predominantly traditional [sometimes displaced] visual sub-languages.

Criticising Cultural Stereotypes In Design

Motivation:

The goal of this course is for learners to develop a critical and respectful engagement with their own culture and those of other people. Through investi-

gation of mediated cultural representations, learners will identify tropes that have emerged to represent cultures across the globe which flow from bias and contribute to cultural stereotyping. Learners will unpack the sources of these tropes to differentiate between cultural stereotypes and authentic self-representation.

Sub-Topics:

- Respectfully using culture
- Cultural Appropriation vs Cultural Appreciation
- Typology, archetypes and stereotypes.

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Differentiate between type, archetype, and stereotype
- Unpack cultural origins of stereotypes
- Appreciate and honour differences Analyse relevance and contextualization
- Define and research cultural appropriation
- Exploring histories of appropriation within specific cultures

Values-Based Design Methodology [Design & Values]

Motivation:

As part of the design development process, learners will uncover the implicit values embedded in a design brief so that the design outcome is in alignment. Students will make personal, social, individual, and corporate value systems explicit. They will reflect on how different value systems and world views influence how a solution is interpreted. They will explore making from different value systems and world views. They will explore the systems that lead to the values [or the values that create the systems]. Learners will explore value systems and how they influence design in different contexts. How they create a design hierarchy – what is high design vs low design, who decides, where does that come from, etc.

5

Sub-Topics:

- Defining values and how they are expressed
- Comparison of social and individual values

- Artefacts from a values-oriented perspective
- Change in value systems over time and the impact of this change on designed outcomes
- The origin of values and the impact on local and global design methods

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Critique objects and systems as manifestations of values
- Differentiate between design methodologies [intuition vs. logic]
- Research pre-modern design history in communities.
- Indigenize design process—from brief to outcome

6

Design Ethnography and Anthropology

Motivation:

Researchers need to recognize the importance of diminishing the difference between subject and object. In that way, research goes beyond observation, it should be based on dialogue and the identification of the researcher with the groups s/he works with. The researcher's approach is not only to collect data, but to contribute to the change goals of those groups.

5

Sub-Topics:

- Correspondence
- "extractive" vs participatory research and ethnography

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

7

Design research situated in pluriversality will evolve in different ways from design research centred in 'modernity'. Futuring will lead to a space for generating conversations around new possibilities for human and other-than-human flourishing.

5 The subject of pluriversal research, as an always caring disposition in the making, guides students to recognize the immensity, heterogeneity, and often overlooked wisdoms and practices that need to be translated, creating greater respect for "other" wisdoms. A seminal assumption here is that those outside the academic-disciplinary field live and bring into existence their own "worlds." Therefore pluriversal design research provides practitioners with elements to respectfully approach otherness and recognize differences and divergences [*language, location, culture, spirituality, class, ethnicity, gender, species, etc.*]. This process should not project the political performance known as the hegemonologue.

This is a voice that excludes, denies, or erases all others and is often infused with euro-modern and anthropocentric biases.

List of Topics Within The Theme:

1. *Pluriversal research epistemologies*
2. *Sustainability and regenerative designs*
3. *Radical imagination, Speculation and Futuring*
4. *Co-design / Participatory design / Co-Creation*
5. *Using and Understanding Oral research histories*

Also for Consideration:

6. *Reframing research*

Pluriversal Research Epistemologies

Motivation:

There is a need to provide a framework for engagement with local and different cultures. Researchers need to recognize that local culture is the starting point that informs the research process. Students will understand that there are multiple ways of doing research, associated with a wide variety of epistemologies. A subject's local context must inform the research process: there is no universal prevailing set of conditions that would inform the research methodology.

Sub-Topics:

- Epistemologies of the south
- Participatory-Action Research / Participatory Research
- Appreciation of body and lived experiences
- Diversity of knowledge and ways of doing
- Pluriverse
- Decolonial feminism

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- The ability to cultivate and expand repertoires of difference and divergence
- Radical Imagining, Speculation and Futuring

Motivation:

Design research should be nested into a framework guided by radical imagining, speculation and futuring. This framework posits that research of existing conditions must be informed by clear goals of what might be.

Sub-Topics:

- Who and what does "design" serve? Communities vs markets
- Participatory ways of establishing clear goals and imagining possibilities
- Non-universal idea of future / Pluriversal futures / Another possible is possible
- Mutual constitution of past, present and future
- Futures construction from daily life

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes

and Rubrics:

- Elaboration of routes of encounters and interaction with otherness.

Co-Design and Participatory Design

Motivation:

As part of the research process, designers need to involve those potentially implicated by any design "solution." This will entail a process of facilitation, discussion, divergence, testing and prototyping and ultimately with convergence on appropriate outcomes. Students will design and work with different tools and techniques that facilitate and stimulate participation. This is a way of doing research through design. Those tools and techniques could be inspired by a diverse range of knowledges, traditions, and disciplines.

Sub-Topics:

- Facilitation
- Relation between subject and object / Values implied

in participation

- Ethical issues surrounding participatory design
- Cross-cultural interaction and cultural competencies

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes

and Rubrics:

- Define co-design and participatory design
- Identify and differentiate the various tools in facilitating co-design processes
- Apply the different tools to an actual case study
- Identify the varying issues related to participatory design processes

Understanding Oral Histories

Motivation:

In the construction of a pluriversal design research should be considered not just the textual tradition of the academia and its reliance on written records and accounts, but also the oral tradition of the communities that the researcher works with.

Sub-Topics:

- Ancestrality and memory
- Relation between “myth” and “science” or “fact.”
- Tools and techniques for stimulating storytelling
- Discourse analysis of oral histories

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes

Rubrics:

Reframing Research

6

- Political motivations of design research
- Data Extractivism
- Knowledge exploitation, and other colonial research approaches

1

6 Communication is foundational to design education. We will explore aspects of speech and representation across text, image, and audio. As learners situate their own communities in relation to other global communities, they will cast a critical eye on the representation of culture across the globe. Of critical importance as well will be a focus on different cultural modalities of narrativity and storytelling. In this topic, we seek to explore global narratives and methods of storytelling, cultural origin stories, and methods. This theme is driven by local origins stories, microhistories, mythologies, and practices to support design students as they find their voice in their practice. Different driving themes may be land-based, sea-based, nature-based, and time-based. There are many different ways of seeing the world, some are rooted in ecology, time, cosmology, cultural memory, ways of knowing, and intergenerational transmission of knowledge. Design is, therefore, about communicating ideas, and this requires

the skill of storytelling, making creative use of language, images, and shared histories. This is a vital skill for design students and can be situated in local cultures. This is also an opportunity for cross-cultural communication as students can compare communication and storytelling myths and methods across different groups, identifying similarities and differences in these practices.

2 **List of Topics Within the Theme:**

1. *Design and Storytelling / Different ways of storytelling / Origin stories by culture*
2. *Cultural transmission through stories*
3. *Alternative methods communication and storytelling [Visual, audio, movement]*
4. *Cultural appropriation, hybridization and appreciation [Ethics and Philosophy]*
5. *Archiving stories [Historiography]*

Design and Storytelling

Motivation:

This course examines the power of storytelling and design. The modern project of design posited universal experiences and therefore assumed universal modes of communication-based on abstract and universalizing imagery and context. In this course, students will be prompted to understand the concept of storytelling as a receptacle of cultural memory and as a powerful mode of communication. In many ways, “storytelling” stands in contrast to abstraction, which has been a favoured mode of communication since the Bauhaus. Storytelling is a method of inquiry that provides a process for an investigation into forms of knowledge. By studying the structural aspects of storytelling, students will find powerful tools to connect to local communities and to their own histories. As students will learn from the work of scholars like

6

Sub-Topics:

- How do designers use storytelling
- How do they locate authentic cultural stories
- Language and imagery in stories
- Creating narratives - how to craft stories
- Ethnography: learning from local oral histories
- Stories: resisting the universal
- Stories and relationality: individualism vs collective,

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Analyse the history of storytelling from unique cultural perspectives
- Analyse origin stories as reflections of personal histories
- Implement storytelling methods in design narratives

3

Cultural Transmission Through Stories

Motivation:

This course assumes that stories are embedded in all cultures. Students will examine stories structurally in terms of transmissibility, origins, and intergenerational impact. Students will be provoked with questions such as: What gets transmitted, what gets forgotten, damaged, erased and why? What makes stories “sticky”? How does this impact transmissibility? What was the motivation behind the stories? Who is telling the stories, and who are the stories being told to? How are stories understood by different audiences? How does this all connect to design? Can we better affect social impact through greater mastery of storytelling’s power? Storytelling also provides pragmatic “micro-histories” to understand sustainable ecological practices better.

6

Sub-Topics:

- Transmitting culture through stories across time
- Cultural values embedded in communication
- Techniques of mass communication
- Storytelling/Communication for behaviour change.
- Learning from micro-histories for positive and sustainable change to the environment
- Understanding local cosmologies and symbologies

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Research origin stories of various cultures
- Identify your personal cultural values transmitted through narratives
- Analyse folkloric stories as emblematic of cultural values
- Develop “sticky” mass communications

4

Alternative Methods of Communication

Motivation:

This is to expose students to a range of communication modalities, based on storytelling. Students will explore storytelling through sound, visuals, dance, theatre, and other creative expressions. Students will approach communication through haptic storytelling and understand the power of movement and sound in addition to more traditional modes of verbal and visual communication. This will enrich students' own design practice and potentially deepen the impact of their communications.

6

Sub-Topics:

- Using sound and music in communication
- Using movement and "improv" techniques to provoke creativity
- Learning from sign language: embodied communication
- Learning from dance notation
- Immersive experiences to enhance community

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes and Rubrics:

- Developing immersive experiences to communicate information
- Research alternative forms of communication [*dance notation, sign language*] to enrich traditional communication

Other Courses for Consideration:

- Cultural appropriation, hybridization, and appreciation
- Archiving stories [*Historiography*]

5

The various environments, physical and virtual contexts of how we teach and learn have embedded issues of inclusion and exclusion. Traditionally, the physical studio has been the space for learning and making. In a more diverse design context, the land and the community may also be significant places of learning.

Empowering education is situated [Shor, 1992], and therefore, sites external to the studios of the educational institutions will also be important venues to embed the curriculum in local culture and contexts, promoting cultural awareness and connections. When developing educational projects with community partners and/or stakeholders from outside the university, such sites can also serve as a valuable source of information—eliciting, for example, ecological knowledge, oral history, and/or collective memory. Places in themselves can provide essential forms of knowledge and lived experiences that are not easily replicated within a conventional classroom.

The dynamics of learning and practising design may shift when the classroom or design studio is situated outside the university—respectful behaviour, cultural protocol, and relationship building can become skills as vital as the craft of sketching and prototyping.

Relationships can also become a foundational concept that underlies learning experiences [especially when situated outside the university]. For instance, in addition to being sensitive to emerging relationships with clients or stakeholders, design students may benefit from a broad ecological understanding of what Arturo Escobar refers to as “relationality.” That is a worldview that emphasises the interconnectedness of all things.

Virtual learning will create opportunities for cross-cultural collaboration, despite the challenges of equitable access in some of these contexts. Virtual learning can also be considered a unique space of learning with its own strengths and opportunities for teaching and

collaborating—different, complementary to, but not necessarily inferior to, physical classrooms. Video conferencing, for instance, may lead to conversations and modes of interaction that are unique to the sensory and psychological experience of digital spaces.

The “design crit” can be considered a time-honoured site of learning. How might we interrogate the crit in terms of embedded issues of power, inclusivity, and relationality? Drawing from the dialogical pedagogy of Paulo Freire, the design crit can take the form of a socially aware, respectful, and meaningful conversation. In other words, conversations between students, teachers, and community partners may provide unique approaches to talking, learning about, and developing an evolving design outcome—an outcome that is shaped by collective community input.

Considering this community-based approach to the design crit, students may benefit from an understanding of participatory forms of research—ways of designing with, and not simply for, people, as well as learning from other forms of designing.

Land, Relationships, Studio, Mobile Studio, Place [Land]-Based Learning, Community-Based Learning

List of Topics Within The Theme:

- 1. In the field: Learning in the community, local spaces e.g. the market, local architecture, local eco-systems etc.*
- 2. ‘The Land’ - Place-based - Place as a site of negotiation*
- 3. Mobile Studio*
- 4. Participatory Placemaking*
- 5. Remote or online spaces*

Learning In Community

Motivation:

This class takes the design experience outside of the academic space and contextualises it in the local community. Students will learn from and with community partners recontextualizing design education, whereas sometimes it can feel removed from the communities in which it takes place. By immersing and

partnering with the community, the design issues and problems are framed within the needs of the community rather than being hypothetical. This real-life and situated learning will facilitate student adaptation to work and post-graduation experiences and exposes students to different models of partnership and working [different from industry preparation]. This exposure will encourage students to question who has the right to problematize issues.

Sub-Topics:

- 6 • Cultural awareness, cultural humility, and healing [in the community].
- Community immersion [*beyond the gated academic environment*]
- Reshaping and relocating design in the community
- Can begin to reform the possibilities of design beyond the academic disciplinary terminological boundaries--by working outside the academic environment.
- Participatory design
- Designers as facilitators, complicators, liaisons, organisers, etc.

- Community engagement mindsets, practices, and strategies
- Healing and restorative justice
- Community Reparations
- Non-extractivist community engagement approaches
- Respect, Humility, co-design, and negotiation
- Community as experts, building trust
- Understanding local systems

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes:

- 8 • Apply appropriate methods for community engagement [inquiries rooted in participatory action, indigenous, ethnographic, and other qualitative methods will most likely inform student projects--quantitative approaches may also be used when appropriate].
- Work collaboratively as a member of a team that includes other students and/or community members.
- Integrate knowledge derived from multiple sources [including community stakeholders].
- Create a design proposal and/or outcome that is informed by community knowledge.
- Evaluate your design proposal and/or outcome through an appropriate mode of gathering feedback

[eg, share back event, meeting with stakeholders, discussion with elders, survey, etc.].

Rubrics:

- Initial design proposal includes introductory text, appropriate ethical considerations, description of design problem/issue, and identification of suitable methods.
- Design outcome provides an appropriate response to community-based needs and results from ongoing engagement.
- Final report includes a reflection and discussion of evaluation.

6

Land-Based Learning

Motivation:

In this course, design students will 'get their hands dirty' and become close to the land and understand agriculture, permaculture, and sustainability in their own cultures and across different cultures. This course may include experiential learning on Indigenous lands. Discussions of Indigenous worldviews, relationality,

and traditional ecological knowledge may inform the learning experience. This can connect with other movements such as 'slow food' and other 'slow' movements, community gardening, and building community through projects, buy local programmes, programs to interrupt large agricultural food chains, etc. A better understanding of 'the land' and working in food systems will help designers to gain a better understanding of issues related to sustainability, systems thinking, and equity, as well as help them envision ways in which they can disrupt and transform these systems.

Sub-Topics:

- Learning from what exists
- Learning from ecology
- Learning from indigenous histories inscribed in land
- Systems thinking [in agriculture, food systems, justice]
- Participatory placemaking
- Participatory service learning
- Participatory expeditionary learning

9

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes:

- Learning outcomes [I'm keeping the learning outcomes relatively consistent from one course to another—modified and adapted to the specifics of each]
- Apply appropriate methods for land-based engagement [depending on the context, Indigenous, ethnographic, phenomenological, and other qualitative methods will most likely inform student projects].
- Work collaboratively as a member of a team that includes other students and/or community members.
- Integrate knowledge derived from multiple sources.
- Create a tangible outcome or proposal that is informed by land-based knowledge.

Rubrics:

- Communication or embodiment of land-based knowledge through a group exhibit, digital space, or other public context.
- Written report based on land-based learning.

Contextual Feedback - New Forms of Critique

Motivation:

Collecting feedback is a skill that designers will need to be successful throughout their careers. In this course, the students will learn to solicit and collect feedback in different types of contexts and scenarios, such as among their peers in the classroom, from people in their communities, and on a broader scale, e.g., nationally or internationally. This class uses a situated learning approach, and therefore the way the feedback is harvested will depend on the situation and context of the class. This class reframes the 'master-student' traditional critique relationship and focuses more on the group and collective experiences.

Sub-topics:

- Multi-directional learning and feedback
- Reframing master/student relationships
- Reframing assumptions assessment and judgement as pedagogy
- Focusing on the potential for abuses of power
- Critiquing the critique

Student-Centred Learning Outcomes:

- Apply appropriate methods for soliciting and collecting feedback based on a situated learning experience.
- Work collaboratively as a member of a team that includes other students and/or community members.
- Integrate knowledge derived from multiple sources [including community stakeholders].
- Create tangible tool[s] or forms of engagement through which to collect feedback, and engage stakeholders and/or participants within the classroom and/or community context.
- Evaluate the appropriateness of your research tool[s] through an appropriate mode of gathering feedback.

Rubrics:

- Design proposal describing, among other things, a community context, along with cultural protocol and sensitivity required when interacting and collecting feedback.
- Tool[s] or form of engagement for collecting feedback from community members—appropriately designed for community context.
- Final report reflecting on the appropriateness of design of the final outcome [tool or form of engagement].

GENERATIVE THEMES AND BIG IDEAS FOR DESIGN EDUCATION

Big ideas are universal ideas, and this working group sought not to create new universals to replace old ones. In the discussions, the group recognized that the big Ideas should look different when realised in different places and contexts. The working group built its ideas by discussing six generative themes, which are listed below, alongside the guiding principles of each discussion.

Pluriversal Ways of Knowing and Making	Through the multiple lenses of culture, epistemology, globality, and locality, the richness of design as practised in different contexts, ecologies, and societies should be explored, emphasising and celebrating this diversity and critically probing notions of "universal."
Respectful Relationality	When people in different cultures who hold different beliefs come into a relationship, deeply rooted feelings of loyalty to one's own culture may impede the relationship. The culture of those in power [or perceived power] may dominate the discourse. In order to avoid such unhealthy power imbalances when working in culturally diverse communities, designers must learn to accept and understand each other's cultural differences. Creating meaningful and mutually respectful cross-cultural relationships can be more challenging than most people think.

7

2

Pluriversal Design Methods and Content

The universalized cultural agenda of design must be deconstructed, dismantled, and re-located into the students' own home/native cultural contexts [and/or any other as applicable], and re-envisioned and re-assembled by them within their culture. Design culture should add to what already exists instead of replacing or imposing a new order. With the knowledge that the local culture is not homogenous or unproblematic either, the aim of this theme is to sensitise and equip the student to empathetically, sensitively, critically, and creatively unpack the various layers and problematics involved, and articulate her/his/their own distinctive contribution in an informed and reflexive way.

Pluriversal Design Research

Design research situated in pluriversality, different from designing research centred in 'modernity', will lead to a space for generating conversations around new possibilities for human and other-than-human flourishing. Pluriversal design research guides students to recognize the immensity, heterogeneity and often overlooked wisdoms and practices that need to be translated, creating greater respect for "other" wisdoms. A seminal assumption here is that those outside the academic-disciplinary field live and bring into existence their own "worlds."Therefore pluriversal design research provides practitioners with elements to respectfully approach otherness and recognize differences and divergences [language, location, culture, spirituality, class, ethnicity, gender, species, etc].

<p>Pluriversal Communication</p>	<p>This theme is driven by local origins stories, microhistories, mythologies, and practices to support design students as they find their voice in their practice. Different driving themes may be land-based, sea-based, nature-based, and time-based. There are many different ways of seeing the world, some are rooted in ecology, time, cosmology, cultural memory, ways of knowing, and intergenerational transmission of knowledge. Design is, therefore, about communicating ideas, and this requires the skill of storytelling, making creative use of language, images, and shared histories. This is also an opportunity for cross-cultural communication as students can compare communication and storytelling myths and methods across different groups, identifying similarities and differences in these practices.</p>
<p>Spaces of Learning</p>	<p>While traditionally, the physical studio has been the space for learning and making, in a pluriversal design context, the land, and the community may also be significant places of learning. The dynamics of learning and practising design may shift when the classroom or design studio is situated outside the university—respectful behaviour, cultural protocol, and relationship building can become skills as vital as the craft of sketching and prototyping. Relationships can also become a foundational concept that underlies learning experiences [especially when situated outside the university]. For instance, in addition to being sensitive to emerging relationships with clients or stakeholders, design students may benefit from a broad ecological understanding of what Arturo Escobar refers to as “relationality.” That is, a worldview that emphasises the interconnectedness of all things.</p>

7

4

The discussions that resulted from the six themes were synthesised into ten big ideas that are presented below:

TEN BIG IDEAS FOR PLURIVERSAL DESIGN EDUCATION

		THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
BIG IDEA 1	Every community practises the design of itself, independent of expert knowledge. People in these communities are the practitioners of their own knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What is an expression of culture? ◦ What is ethnography? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Apply ethnographic research methods ◦ Apply co-creation and co-design methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Colonisation/decolonisation ◦ Neo- and Auto-colonisation ◦ Suppression of indigenous cultures and worldviews
BIG IDEA 2	Unlike modernist traditions, relational approaches to design address multiple ways in which things are connected: nature and culture, mind and body, and us and them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ How place-based communities understand fundamental relations within the community and between the community and others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Model the problem at hand ◦ Think of causal networks rather than causal chains ◦ Activate diverse networks of commitment within communities /organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Modernist principles of universality, social progress, and scientific and technological objectivism

7

5

Design with and by, not for people. The role of the designer when working in another culture is that of a facilitator, not the decider. Designers should also disclose what they intend to gain from observing other cultures

THINGS TO KNOW:

- Problem framing is inherently subjective and must be negotiated and reaffirmed with and by stakeholders throughout the design process
- The designer is an observer, discloser, and facilitator

THINGS TO DO:

- Include all stakeholders in a collaborative design process, ensuring that all voices are heard
- Facilitate conversations through "propositional" models and prototypes that translate and respect various stakeholder views on the situation
- Actively engage stakeholders in the prioritisation of competing wants and needs. Co-design, co-create methods [under Methods group]

THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:

- Forms/tools of storytelling
- Cultural histories of various under-represented groups [Collective and consultative creative and decision-making processes?]

There is no one universal design history

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Designers need to learn how to study alternative design histories ◦ The dominant design history that is currently being taught around the world tends to favour the Western narrative, which focuses on Eurocentricity and often ignores the many local influences across many other regions in the world 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Understand the cultural-specific design history of the community for which you are designing. Study how different communities use or do things differently by taking into consideration local circumstances [geography, climate, culture, politics, access to resources and technology, etc.] ◦ Make design decisions that are relevant to the region or the community for which you are designing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Cultural competence ◦ Historical research ◦ Ethnographic research ◦ Local design traditions and histories

We need to introduce radical empathy in design

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Radical empathy calls for more than just gaining a basic understanding of the challenges that people experience ◦ This is a process that encourages people to actively consider other people’s points of view and circumstances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Identify and describe the challenges experienced by various individuals and their local communities ◦ Engage in respectful exploration with community partners ◦ Propose design solutions and analyse their impact on personal well-being 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Ethics ◦ Relationality ◦ Respectful collaboration ◦ Interdependence

BIG IDEA 6

The studio is not the only place where design happens

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Traditionally, physical environments such as classrooms and design studios have been seen as spaces for learning and making ◦ In a more diverse design context, the land and the community should also be environments where the location-specific or land-based design takes place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Learn from people by engaging with them in their personal and community spaces and built environments ◦ Learn about the local ecosystems and understand how the community co-exists with its natural surroundings ◦ Learn from indigenous histories inscribed in the land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Cultural awareness, respect, and humility ◦ Community immersion ◦ Negotiations ◦ Participatory design ◦ Systems thinking principles ◦ Local systems and ways of living ◦ The 'field'

Designers need to design for resilience and change

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ There are many vulnerable communities that may be exposed to disruptive and volatile events that will threaten their well-being ◦ How can we study resilience in the context of crisis, disruptive change, and social well-being? ◦ How can we design adaptive, resilient social responses to critical situations? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Learn about everyday solutions that have been created in response to disruptions or crises in the past ◦ Anticipate possible disruption factors that may affect a community or an organisation ◦ Envision a future scenario that includes adaptive strategies for resilience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Resilience theory ◦ Crisis leadership ◦ Futures thinking ◦ Speculative design ◦ Degrowth

Design can future-proof marginalised cultures

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can designers help reclaim or revive local design subcultures that have been marginalised? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse local and immediate culture for constituent influences and origins Analyse ethical, spiritual, and aesthetic components of design culture Research and track how cultures evolve over time and assimilate various influences Analyse "modernity" as a driver of culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> History and cultural context Ethnography Participatory design Deep listening

BIG IDEA 9

Designers should understand what "industry" means not only on a macro level but also at a micro and local level and in a range of scales of production

THINGS TO KNOW:

- Designers working with local knowledges and skills of production can help leverage a community's economic health and sustainability. Designers can help apply social innovation methodologies to amplify local existing expertise

THINGS TO DO:

- Research and respect local networks of the supply chain, methods of production, and craft knowledge

THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:

- Sustainability
- Social Innovation
- Authentic cultural expression vs market commodification
- Non-monetary exchange?

Designers need to learn how to “read” the cultural values in the stories that communities share.

THINGS TO KNOW:	THINGS TO DO:	THINGS TO BE FAMILIAR WITH:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local origin stories, micro-histories, mythologies, and practices can support designers to find the authentic voice of the communities that they are working with, and this can help them to situate themselves better with these communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage with the creative use of language, storytelling, shared imagery and histories Explore local myths, legends, and folklore 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Storytelling, and Cultural memory Intergenerational transmission of knowledge Cross-cultural communication Cultural relationship to time and space Ways of knowing

References

2022. About. Accessed December 20. <https://www.futureofdesignededucation.org/about>.

Capra, Fritjof, and Pier Luigi Luisi. 2019. *The Systems View of Life: A Unifying Vision*. Cambridge (UK): Cambridge University Press.

Cordova, V. F., Kathleen Dean Moore, Kurt Peters, Theodore S. Jojola, Amber Lacy, and Linda Hogan. 2007. *How It Is: The Native American Philosophy of V.F. Cordova*. Tucson, AZ: The University of Arizona Press.

Dei, George J. 2014. "Indigenizing the School Curriculum." *African Indigenous Knowledge and the Disciplines*, In G. Emeagwali & G. S. Dei (Eds.), *African Indigenous Knowledge and the Disciplines* (pp. 165-180). essay, Sense Publishers. doi:10.1007/978-94-6209-770-4_13.

Escobar, Arturo. 2018. *Designs for the Pluriverse: Radical Interdependence, Autonomy, and the Making of Worlds*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.

Gutiérrez, Alfredo. 2022. *DISSOCONS Diseños del sur, de los sures, otros, con otros nombres*. Manizales.

McIntosh, Alastair. 2005. *Soil and Soul People versus Corporate Power*. London: Aurum.

Perry, Mia. 2020. "Pluriversal Literacies: Affect and Relationality in Vulnerable Times." *Reading Research Quarterly* 56 (2): 293-309. doi:10.1002/rrq.312.

Pinto, Alvaro Vieira. 2020. *Consciência e Realidade Nacional*. Vol. 1. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Contraponto.

Reiter, Bernd. 2018. *Constructing the Pluriverse: The Geopolitics of Knowledge*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.

Shor, Ira. 1992. *Empowering Education: Critical Teaching for Social Change*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Willis, Anne-Marie. 2006. "Ontological Designing." *Design Philosophy Papers* 4 (2): 69-92. doi:10.2752/144871306x13966268131514.

THE FUTURE OF
PLURIVERSAL
DESIGN
EDUCATION